

Volumetric Behaviour in Mixed Aqueous Solvents. Part-I. Partial Molal Volumes of Transfer of Tris(hydroxymethyl)aminomethane (Tris) from Water to Aqueous Ethanol and Aqueous t-Butanol at 303.15 and 313.15 K

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The partial molal volume of tris(hydroxymethyl)aminomethane(tris) was obtained in the concentration range 0.02–0.50 M in water and in aqueous solutions containing 10, 20, 30, 40 and 50% (w/w) of alcohol (ethanol or t-butanol). Anomalous behaviour was observed in the region of maximum structure enhancement of water by the two alcohols. Partial molal volumes of transfer of tris from water to the aqueous alcohol solutions were calculated. Values for the partial molal expansibility of tris were obtained as a function of solvent composition from measurements at 303.15 and 313.15 K. The results are interpreted in terms of solvent-solvent and solute-solvent interactions.

WHEN a solute is dissolved in water, the volume of the solution is generally, but not always, higher than that of water alone. The volume increase, however, is less than would be expected from simple additivity. Put differently, the excess partial molal volume (\bar{V}^E) of the solute is negative. This value is defined as the difference between the partial molal volume of the solute in the solvent (\bar{V}_2) and its volume in the pure state (V_2), i.e. $\bar{V}^E = \bar{V}_2 - V_2$. These negative values, observed for both electrolytes and non-electrolytes, reflect the structural dynamism of liquid water and its capacity, established in a number of cases, to accommodate the solute molecules in clathrate-like cages¹. The \bar{V}_2 value itself, however, may increase or decrease as the solute molality is altered. Most solutes in water possess positive $d\bar{V}_2/dm$ slopes, with the implication that the solute causes a collapse of order in water. In a few cases, however, notably in some aqueous alcohol solutions, negative slopes are obtained at low alcohol concentrations, with a minimum in the \bar{V}_2 vs m plots corresponding to well-defined highly ordered liquid structure. Under these conditions the alcohol is said to enhance the structure of water and the minimum corresponds to a composition at which the alcohol exerts its maximum long-range structure promotion effects. It is noteworthy that several physico-chemical properties, such as compressibility of alcohol-water mixtures and critical micelle concentrations, exhibit extrema in the region of maximum structure promotion². Several models have been put forward for the structure of liquid water, such as the 'flickering cluster' model of Frank and Wen³. In this model, water consists of two types of species in equilibrium: the first is composed of highly

hydrogen-bonded, tetrahedrally shaped clusters and the second is dense monomeric units. The addition of a solute perturbs this equilibrium. The designation 'structure maker' is given to a solute that favours cluster formation and 'structure breaker' to one that favours the break-up into smaller units.

Very few studies on the volumetric properties of solutes in mixed solvents have appeared in the literature⁴⁻⁷. In such ternary systems, due consideration must be given to solvent-solvent, solvent-solute and solute-solute interactions. The latter type may be disregarded when working with very dilute solutions or when extrapolations to infinite dilution are made. The purpose of this work is to gain insight into the possible nature of such interactions. This is achieved via the addition of a solute to aqueous ethanol and aqueous t-butanol solutions of varying alcohol content. The two alcohols were selected because they both exhibit minima in their partial molal volumes in aqueous solutions, but for different reasons. Thus, whereas ethanol promotes the structure of water through a hydrophilic type of interaction, t-butanol does so via predominantly hydrophobic forces^{2,5,8}. The investigation was initiated with the important biological buffer tris-(hydroxymethyl)amino methane (tris). This solute was selected because it contains two kinds of functional groups, viz. one amino and three hydroxyls, whose anticipated individual contributions to the partial molal volume of this solute in water may be estimated from studies on individual alcohols⁹ and amines^{10,11}. In addition, tris does not hydrolyse to any appreciable extent in either water or in the mixed solvents (see below), thereby effectively removing from consideration the complicating influences of ionic interactions arising from partial hydrolysis or dissociation of the solute.

Experimental

A commercial sample of tris was recrystallised twice from 30% aqueous methanol and dried under reduced pressure for 48 h (m. p. 169–70°). Ethanol and t-butanol (AnalaR) were used as such. Water was double-distilled and deionised before use ($\kappa < 2 \times 10^{-6} \Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$). Thermostat temperatures were accurate to within 0.01 and were monitored by means of a thermocouple probe. Weights were measured to five decimal places. The densities (pycnometers) were accurate to within 0.00005 units. All measurements were air-corrected. Solutions were reequilibrated at 25.0° for 30 min before weighing. At least three independent sets of measurements were obtained at each solvent composition, each set comprising about eight different tris concentrations.

Results and Discussion

The results were fitted to the equation,

$$V = am^2 + bm + c \quad (1)$$

where, V is the volume (in cm^3) of solution containing 1000 g of the cosolvent, m the molality and a , b and c are constants. Values of V were calculated from density measurements and plotted against m . A computer linear regression program was employed to evaluate the constants. The partial molal volume of the solute (\bar{V}_2) is then obtained as a function of molality by differentiation of equation (1),

$$\bar{V}_2 = 2am + b \quad (2)$$

Table 1 summarises the results. It is to be noted that the constant b may be identified with the infinite

dilution partial molal volume (\bar{V}_2^0) which in turn is numerically equal to the infinite dilution apparent molal volume (ϕ_2^0). Values for the infinite dilution partial molal expansibility (\bar{E}_2^0), defined by $d\bar{V}_2^0/dT$, are also tabulated. The standard deviation in the partial molal volumes varied in the range 0.06–0.08 $\text{cm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$, with the higher deviations occurring in the low concentration range.

The partial molal volume of transfer of tris from water to the mixed solvent ($\Delta\bar{V}_{tr}$) is an important thermodynamic value and constitutes a good indicator of structural interactions. This quantity, given by $V_{\text{solvent}} - V_{\text{water}}$, may be calculated for tris concentrations upto 0.5 m by using equation (2) and the data of Table 1. In the corresponding infinite dilution value ($\Delta\bar{V}_{tr}^0$) given by $b_{\text{solvent}} - b_{\text{water}}$, solute-solute interactions are eliminated and the transfer function is determined by the nature of the cosolvent and its interaction with the solute. The $\Delta\bar{V}_{tr}^0$ values at 303.15 and 313.15 K are plotted in Fig. 1 for both the water-ethanol and water-t-butanol cosolvents. It is apparent that all the transfer values are positive and that well-pronounced anomalies with both the cosolvent systems exist in the vicinity of 10% (w/w) alcohol. The location of the anomalies is particularly noteworthy since they occur in the region of structure enhancement of water by the alcohols. The magnitude and position of maximum enhancement are temperature dependent. For ethanol at 303.15 K, there is a broad minimum extending from ca. 9 to 18% (w/w) ethanol². This minimum deepens and becomes sharper as the temperature is lowered with a shift towards the higher composition. In the case of t-butanol, the minimum shifts from ca.

TABLE 1—VALUES FOR CONSTANTS a , b AND c OF EQUATION (1) AND \bar{E}_2^0 FOR TRIS IN WATER-ETHANOL AND WATER-t-BUTANOL AS A FUNCTION OF SOLVENT COMPOSITION*

	In water-ethanol (ethanol %, w/w)					
	0	10	20	30	40	50
a	5.72	-8.15	6.65	4.18	-1.68	-1.62
	8.89	-7.88	4.86	2.02	0.60	-1.90
b	86.34	93.48	87.81	90.26	90.94	91.99
	84.59	94.72	87.37	91.62	91.51	96.38
c	1 004.39	1 020.36	1 036.40	1 054.45	1 076.55	1 101.77
	1 007.83	1 024.96	1 043.59	1 062.78	1 087.28	1 113.15
\bar{E}_2^0	-0.17	0.12	-0.04	0.14	0.06	0.44
	In water-t-butanol (t-butanol %, w/w)					
	0	10	20	30	40	50
a	5.72	-11.01	-1.99	-2.10	-3.03	-1.00
	8.89	-8.95	5.54	0.44	-5.08	-3.15
b	86.34	96.13	91.82	89.19	91.57	90.70
	84.59	95.25	90.40	91.40	93.24	92.64
c	1 004.39	1 018.72	1 035.88	1 060.39	1 087.87	1 117.79
	1 007.83	1 024.19	1 044.04	1 068.70	1 097.08	1 126.08
\bar{E}_2^0	-0.17	-0.09	-0.14	0.22	0.17	0.12

*In each row, the first set of values is at 303.15 K and the second at 313.15 K ; Units : volume, $\text{cm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$ expansibility, $\text{cm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$.

Fig. 1 Infinite dilution partial molal volumes of transfer of tris from water to aqueous ethanol (1a) and aqueous t-butanol (1b) as a function of alcohol content : (O) 303.15 and (●) 313.15 K

8% (w/w) t-butanol at 323.15 K to ca. 14% at 288.15 K³. Thus, for both the cosolvent systems, the maxima in the partial molal volumes of tris almost mirror the minima in the partial molal volumes of the each alcohol in its binary solution with water.

At this point it is appropriate to compare the experimental value of \bar{V}_2^0 for tris in pure water with one estimated from measurements on amines and alcohols. t-Butylamine is an analogue of tris in the sense that the OH groups of tris are replaced by H atoms. The values of \bar{V}_2^0 and \bar{V}^{0E} for this amine in water are 91.24 and $-10 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$ at 298.15 K, respectively¹¹ with the large negative \bar{V}^{0E} value attributed to the accommodation of this amine within solvate cages. On the basis of expansibility values, the interaction of this amine with water is believed to be dominated by the hydrophobic rather than the amino group, and the molecule as a whole is designated as a hydrophobic structure-maker¹¹. When \bar{V}_2^0 for t-butylamine in water is compared with the value of $86.34 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$ for tris at 303.15 K (Table 1), it is readily apparent that replacement of three H atoms by three OH groups causes a further decrease in the volume by ca. $4.9 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$. Thus, for the

transformation $\text{H} \rightarrow \text{OH}$, \bar{V}^{0E} is ca. $-1.6 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$. Literature values for this processes, based on studies on polyols⁹, range from -1 to $2 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$. The finding that the \bar{V}^{0E} value obtained in this work is somewhat below the lower limit for pure alcohols, suggests that the NH_2 group in tris enhances the order beyond the normal expectation, based on the behaviour of simple amines. It is possible that it does so by engaging in, as well as promoting, cooperative hydrogen bonding within the open caged structure it helps to create. Similar comparisons could not be made in the alcohol solutions due to the inavailability of the requisite literature data.

The change in volume of a solute upon dissolution in a solvent may be regarded as the sum of electrostrictive, structural and cage contributions¹². In the case of tris, electrostriction is negligible, as this term is used to denote the decrease in volume arising from the interaction of ions with the solvent. Since tris does not hydrolyse to any appreciable extent in water as well as in the mixed solvents, the charge on this molecule is effectively zero. This conclusion is based on the relatively low K_b values for tris, viz. 1.2×10^{-6} in water¹³ and 6.6×10^{-6} in 50% aqueous methanol at 298 K¹⁴. Since the fraction hydrolysed is roughly given by $(K_b/m)^{1/2}$, it is apparent that even at the smallest concentration employed in this work, ca. 0.02 *m*, less than one percent of the tris molecules are hydrolysed. The shrinkage in the volume of tris upon dissolution in water is thus due to structural and cage factors only. The former arises from the ordering of the cosolvent into compact units around the solute and the latter refers the accommodation of the solute within interstitial spaces in the solvent. Furthermore, at the higher concentrations, intermolecular hydrogen bonding is expected to cause additional reduction in the partial molal volume, an effect reflected in negative values for the constant *a* of equation (1). This is most notably observed with the 10% solutions, for both the water-ethanol and water-t-butanol cosolvents (Table 1). Here, it is probable that the significant solute-solute interaction partly reflects the strong solvent-solvent affinity with the concomitant unfavourable energy involved in breaking a highly enhanced cosolvent structure in order to accommodate solute molecules.

Fig. 1 reveals that the anomaly, with both the alcohols, occurs within an increasing trend in $\Delta\bar{V}_2^0$ as the solvent becomes richer in alcohol. The regular trend itself may be explained on the basis that alcohol addition acts to loosen and squeeze the water out of the hydration sphere of tris, even possibly rupturing the caged structure. This supposition is supported by the occurrence of the anomalies in the region of structure enhancement of water by the two alcohols. In this region, it is reasonable to expect the alcohol to be most effective in competing for the water molecules within the solvation sphere of tris. Put differently, it may be stated that whereas tris promotes the structure of

pure water, it acts to disrupt the enhanced structure of water-alcohol, largely through competition for H-bonding.

Further support for this view is derived from the values of the infinite dilution partial molal expansibility, \bar{E}_2^0 . Inspection of Table 1 shows that whereas \bar{E}_2^0 for tris in water is negative ($-0.17 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$) it is positive in most of the cosolvent systems. The negative sign indicates that water expands more rapidly than its tris solution. This may be rationalised by postulating that cooperative hydrogen bonding is so high and pervasive that a 10° rise in temperature has little or no effect upon its extent. Alternately, it may be said that tris molecules fit into strong compact cages that require a high activation energy to collapse. The two explanations are in fact compatible, since the energy required to rupture a solvent cage is expected to increase when the solvent becomes involved in strong, cooperative bonding, with the caged solute. By contrast, the \bar{E}_2^0 value for tris in 10% ethanol is positive ($0.12 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$). This is in accord with the earlier supposition that alcohol addition loosens the bound water molecules, with the extent of this loosening increasing, as expected, with temperature. The net effect is to cause the solute to expand more rapidly than the solvent, leading to the observed positive expansibility value. In t-butanol-water, on the other hand, the maximum positive \bar{E}_2^0 value occurs at 30% alcohol. This may represent a low point in the transition from hydrophilic solvation by water to hydrophobic solvation by t-butanol. It may, however, be premature to attempt to draw too many conclusions before more data are accumulated in similar ternary systems.

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References

1. H. S. FRANK and M. W. EVANS, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1945, **13**, 507.
2. F. FRANKS in "Physico-chemical Processes in Mixed Aqueous Solvents", ed. F. FRANKS, Elsevier, New York, 1967.
3. H. S. FRANK and W. Y. WEN, *Discuss. Faraday Soc.*, 1957, **24**, 133.
4. J. S. SANDHU, P. KAUR and U. KASHYAP, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1986, **63**, 729.
5. J. S. SANDHU and G. SINGH, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1988, **65**, 602.
6. A. MISHRA and J. AHLUWALIA, *J. Chem. Soc., Faraday Trans.*, 1981, 1469.
7. G. DI PAOLA and B. BELLEAU, *Can. J. Chem.*, 1978, **56**, 1827.
8. E. M. ARNETT in "Physico-chemical Processes in Mixed Aqueous Solvents", ed. F. FRANKS, Elsevier, New York, 1967.
9. C. JOLICOEUR and G. LACROIX, *Can. J. Chem.*, 1976, **54**, 614.
10. M. V. KAULGUD and K. J. PATIL, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1976, **80**, 138.
11. M. V. KAULGUD, V. J. BHAGDE and A. SHRIVASTAVA, *J. Chem. Soc., Faraday Trans.*, 1982, 313.
12. F. J. MILLERO in "Water and Aqueous Solutions", ed. K. A. HORNE, Wiley, New York, 1972, Chap. 13.
13. R. G. BATES and H. B. HETZER, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1961, **65**, 667.
14. M. WOODHEAD, M. PAABO, R. A. ROBINSON and R. G. BATES, *J. Res. Natl. Bur. Std. (A)*, 1965, **69**, 263.